

13C-MFA experimental data profiles

Streptomyces lividans TK24 *pIJ486* run 1

Streptomyces lividans TK24 pIJ486 run 2

Streptomyces lividans TK24 *pIJ486-vsi-celA* run 1

Streptomyces lividans TK24 *pIJ486-vsi-celA* run 2

